

ELEVATE: Enabling and Leveraging Climate Action Towards Net-Zero Emissions

Grant agreement no. 101056873

HORIZON-CL5-2021-D1-01

D5.2 – Assessment of universal access to basic needs

Work Package: 5

Due date of deliverable: 31st July 2025

Actual submission date: 4th August 2025

Start date of project: 1st September 2022

Duration: 48 months

The lead beneficiary for this deliverable: IIASA

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Project co-funded by the European Commission within the Horizon Europe Programme (2021-2027)		
Dissemination Level		
PU	Public	√

1. Changes with respect to the description of work

No changes compared to the task description.

2. Dissemination and uptake

See report below.

3. Short summary of results (<250 words)

This report explores how ensuring Decent Living Standards (DLS) for all – covering essential services like nutrition, housing, transport, and health – affects global energy use and climate mitigation. We use the DESIRE model with bottom-up country-level information on energy requirements for DLS and integrate it with the MESSAGEix-GLOBIOM framework. We assess energy needs, gaps, and related emissions for ten global regions based on an assessment of 172 countries.

In this report, we compare two scenarios to show initial results. A "Reference" SSP2-based mitigation pathway and a "Minimum Needs" (MN) scenario that starts from this Reference but additionally closes energy deprivation by 2040 while remaining within the same carbon budget of 520 GtCO₂ between 2025 and 2100.

Achieving DLS for all by 2040 increases global energy demand modestly (4% in 2030, 9% in 2040, 5% in 2050) but significantly increases in Sub-Saharan Africa (35% in 2030, 68% in 2040, 31% in 2050), the region with the highest DLS deprivation.

Staying within the same emissions budget remains manageable through efficiency gains and clean energy transitions. Emissions associated with DLS provisioning are projected to drop in all regions due to cleaner - and eventually net-negative - energy systems. While the MN scenario leads to slightly higher short-term emissions in developing regions, these are offset by deeper reductions or carbon removal in wealthier regions. Coal phase-outs timing in developing regions is not delayed.

This analysis illustrates a pathway of addressing global climate targets and human development simultaneously, when inequality and climate policy are designed together.

4. Evidence of accomplishment

See report below and this published article in which the DESIRE model is described in more detail in: *Kikstra, Jarmo S., et al. (2025). "Closing decent living gaps in energy and emissions scenarios: introducing DESIRE". Environmental Research Letters 20, 054038. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1748-9326/adc3ad>*

Version log

Version	Date	Released by	Nature of Change
1	24-06-2025	Jarmo S. Kikstra, Elina Brutschin, Tommaso Zaini	First draft
2	31-07-2025	Jarmo S. Kikstra, Elina Brutschin, Tommaso Zaini	Incorporated feedback from PBL (Mark Dekker) and COPPE (Talita Borges Cruz)

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1. Introduction

Climate scenarios explore a range of plausible futures, often focusing on what is required under current trends to meet climate targets such as the Paris Agreement. However, current trends maintain inequalities, and many remain deprived of minimum needs. To understand what climate policies could look like in more positive futures with strong socioeconomic development, we explore futures that reduce inequality by providing Decent Living Standards (DLS) for all.

In this report, we examine the climate implications of providing universal access to DLS. We do so by integrating bottom-up information about minimum energy and service demands for 172 countries in the MESSAGEix-GLOBIOM integrated assessment model (IAM).

While previous studies have quantified minimum energy needs for well-being, this work advances the state of the art by bringing minimum needs research to climate scenario modeling. Bridging these two fields allows us to understand how (much) achieving DLS alters energy transitions and mitigation pathways.

The main question we try to answer is: how does providing DLS for all that do not yet have it affect the global energy transition, while maintaining the same climate target?

Here, we explore how a **"Minimum Needs" (MN)** mitigation scenario that ensures everyone reaches DLS differs from a **"Reference"** mitigation scenario which reflects common default model setups in the climate mitigation pathway literature. Both have the same carbon budget between 2025 and 2100, staying well-below 2C warming.

First, we review the existing literature on DLS in Section 2, which provides a comprehensive and yet pragmatic approach to estimating a minimum resource requirement for meeting human needs. Second, in Section 3, we quantify 'just corridors' by looking at the current energy and emissions footprints of DLS and looking at scenarios that meet the Paris Agreement. After discussing how DLS is integrated into the MESSAGEix-GLOBIOM framework in Section 4, we look at projections of energy needs, emissions, and energy system characteristics under net-zero emissions pathways that improve justice and equity by achieving minimum levels of decent living for all by 2040.

2. Decent Living Standards (DLS) concept

Disclaimer

This text is adapted from the publication:

- Kikstra, Jarmo S., et al. (2025). "Closing decent living gaps in energy and emissions scenarios: introducing DESIRE". *Environmental Research Letters* 20, 054038.

2.1 The DLS Framework in the Context of Climate Action and Sustainable Development

The Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) aim to simultaneously achieve objectives related to eradicating poverty, promoting socio-economic development and preserving the natural environment. However, most countries currently fall short of meeting these social and environmental targets concurrently (Fanning et al., 2022). Therefore, there is a need to create and understand scenarios that simultaneously support human flourishing and meet environmental targets. Energy systems play a major role in this: energy use is directly related to eradicating poverty and reversing ecological degradation, in particular climate change and air pollution. Several frameworks have been suggested to define desirable futures either from an ecological perspective and development perspective or both, such as the 'safe and just Earth system boundaries' (Gupta et al., 2023; Rockström et al., 2023), linked to 'doughnut' or 'safe and just operating space' (Fanning et al., 2022; O'Neill et al., 2018; Raworth, 2017), the 'sustainable development target space' (van Vuuren et al., 2022), or 'consumption corridors' (Fuchs et al., 2021) and 'production corridors' (Bärnthaler & Gough, 2023). The concept of 'decent living standards' (DLS; (Rao & Min, 2018a)) has gained traction as a lower boundary, or minimum requirement, for supporting human well-being in these concepts (e.g. (Schlesier et al., 2024)).

The current consensus is that eradicating extreme income poverty, for instance defined as the World Bank's global international poverty line of 2.15\$ (PPP 2017)/person/day does not put climate goals at risk (Bruckner et al., 2022; Wollburg et al., 2023; Rao & Min, 2018b; Riahi et al., 2012, 2022; Van Vuuren et al., 2015). However, such a low poverty line tracks a 'standard of miserable subsistence' (Alston, 2020) and does not track the multidimensional achievement of DLS (Kikstra et al., 2021), meaning that people could still be living in unhealthy circumstances such as slums without safe water provisioning or thermal comfort.

2.2 Understanding the Decent Living Standards (DLS) Concept

The concept of DLS aims to provide clarity on the material prerequisites for human well-being (Rao & Min, 2018a). The concept is multidimensional and goes beyond other existing multidimensional poverty indicators by enabling explicitness about the means of living conditions and social participation. It is a pragmatic, normative framework that enables the quantification of environmental impacts of (ambitious) poverty eradication.

The Decent Living Standards (DLS) approach, introduced by Narasimha Rao and colleagues (Rao et al., 2019; Rao and Min, 2018) in the context of access to key services, provides a framework for conceptualizing and measuring basic material prerequisites for human well-being. In using this framework, researchers attempt to define a set of universal, irreducible and essential material conditions for achieving basic human wellbeing, together with quantitative thresholds for specific indicators. The satisfaction of these quantitative thresholds can then be operationalized for societies, accounting for differences in provisioning systems and local customs. Generally, applications steer away from capturing individual preferences or hedonic

positions. Analyses differ in the extent to which local customs and provisioning systems are accounted for, balancing between 'capturing current provisioning systems' and 'capturing an efficient potential minimum material requirement'. Most research on quantifying resource requirements has been done for energy requirements (e.g., Goldemberg et al., 1985; Kikstra et al., 2021; Millward-Hopkins, 2022; Millward-Hopkins et al., 2020; Rao et al., 2019), with recent work advancing the minimum requirement of materials (Vélez-Henao and Pauliuk, 2023) and a large range of indicators using life cycle analysis (Schlesier et al., 2024). While this approach offers several advantages, there are also downsides. This section briefly outlines both the strengths and limitations of the DLS framework.

Compared to many other traditional poverty measures, the DLS are relatively comprehensive. The aim is to encompass a wide range of living conditions and means of social participation, allowing for a more concrete identification at the intersection of well-being and infrastructural planning. The normative foundation of the DLS is grounded in theories of justice, including the capability approach and concepts of basic needs. Through its measurability, the DLS offer an avenue to develop environmental impacts of poverty eradication efforts through modelling resource gaps and resource needs. These can then be linked to (dynamic) forward-looking planning efforts. And while the proposed set is meant to be a universal set of standards, the specific thresholds are very flexible, meaning the DLS can be operationalized based on the particular needs of the analysis, where context-specific considerations may point to different thresholds specifications used in this report.

At the same time, any quantification related to the concept of human needs faces limitations, some of which cannot be overcome. One of the core critiques on using the DLS approach is that determining precise thresholds for material requirements is difficult or nearly impossible, and potentially arbitrary. This critique relates quite closely to the general critique of cultural relativism; the understanding that what exactly constitutes a "decent" standard of living may vary significantly across cultures and contexts, challenging the universality of the approach. In this light, the original DLS proposal (Rao and Min, 2018) explicitly calls for operationalizing quantities of satisfiers based on local consultation (e.g., diets), welcoming a certain level of incorporation of cultural contexts. Not only can needs be culture-specific, they can also be time-specific. As societies develop, perceptions of basic needs (together with preferences and subjective well-being) tend to evolve, leading to increased challenges in understanding to what extent static standards for longer planning time horizons remain adequate. In critiques, this adequacy is mainly to be connected to whether the DLS can still be a useful minimum, with various preferences (with increasing affluence) pointing more to an expansion of the set of services to be included, not a contraction of the set, with no arguments for excluding any of the current constituents. Following Rao and Min (page 232), including more constituents is possible when "a DLS must either be necessary and indispensable, or globally desired", with a good or service belong in a DLS only if it satisfies conditions (a) AND (b) AND (either c.1 or c.2) below: "only if it satisfies conditions (a) AND (b) AND (either c.1 or c.2): (a) It satisfies at least one basic need or capability (that is, it either helps fulfill a dimension, or prevents harm to people's own fulfillment); (b) It doesn't harm the fulfillment of anybody's needs or capabilities; (c.1) It is the only satisfier of at least

one basic need/capability; (c.2) It is one of many competing satisfiers, but it is overwhelmingly preferred at a global scale for at least one dimension. The bar must be set high for such support—goods must be owned or desired by an overwhelming majority populations in all countries where they are available and affordable.”

Building on the previous points, it is important that standards are developed and implemented through a procedurally fair process. This means involving all relevant stakeholders to ensure that specific material standards do not reflect only external values. Otherwise, they could undermine local autonomy or harm the ability of communities to meet their needs or develop their capabilities (as highlighted in principle (b)). This should help prevent the results of research using the DLS from being used to justify authoritarian or paternalistic approaches. Lastly, as any ‘basket’ approach, it does not capture all possible needs and sub-needs, but only represents a selection—often limited by the focus (e.g., energy needs) and by what can be measured, not capturing the full breadth of human needs (see e.g., Doyal and Gough, 1991). In this research, we follow Rao and Min (page 234) who write: “this project doesn’t allow a comprehensive assessment of a DLS, but rather focuses on essential material elements. Any DLS must include political, civil and psychological “goods” (whether they are considered to be rights, liberties, or other forms of entitlements), ... [which we] take ... for granted, but limit their operationalization to aspects that principally entail material needs, namely the means of social engagement. For example, psychological wellbeing (e.g., self-esteem), once people have other elements of a DLS, such as good health and education, depends far less on material possessions than on how people treat each other. Political institutions and granting political rights do require physical infrastructure to function (e.g., voting infrastructure, national defense), however to our knowledge there is little basis to link ‘good’ institutions (e.g. democracy vs. autocracy) to the extent of infrastructure. We set this aside for further research. What non-material societal pre-conditions are necessary to ensure that political institutions provide decent political/social rights is a complex and deep question, which we do not have the scope to address.”.

While the DLS reflects characteristics of a ‘modern’ society — particularly those aligned with Western consumption patterns — many of its elements are increasingly valued across the globe and are therefore included in our assessment of current and future needs. Future work could explicitly explore how the components of the DLS basket might evolve over time as part of scenario development. However, this report does not address such structural changes. Instead, it focuses on behavioural and value shifts within high-consumption contexts, without examining changes to the underlying minimum material requirements.

Other limitations to the approach have the potential to be overcome by further research. One clear example, which is explicitly addressed in this manuscript, is the potential for tension with sustainability goals. Achieving universal DLS may conflict with environmental sustainability goals in some contexts, necessitating careful consideration of trade-offs. In this manuscript, we analyse the concurrent pursuit of social and environmental goals to illustrate the nuances in this tension.

Therefore, while the DLS approach offers valuable insights for assessing human wellbeing and development needs, these insights will (necessarily) always only be

partial, and careful application and ongoing refinement is important. Future work would benefit from amongst others (a) explicitly addressing known limitations through sensitivity analyses or methodological refinements; (b) combining the DLS framework with complementary beyond-GDP indicators; (c) regularly updating and adapting DLS metrics to reflect changing societal norms and technological advancements; and (d) engaging in participatory processes to understand difference in varying local perspectives for DLS operationalisation.

In sum, the DLS approach can be seen as a pragmatic, partial, implementation of the material aspects of a capabilities and human needs approach to human welfare (e.g. (Doyal & Gough, 1991; Max-Neef, 1991; Nussbaum, 2003; Robeyns, 2005; Sen, 1993)), ensuring a (multidimensional) minimum for all people to achieve and do what they have reason to value.

2.3 Key Constituents of the Decent Living Standards

The DLS are thus a basket of services. In this report, we use the services as specified in Table 1. They are meant to serve as a universal set of services that provide a decent minimum for calculating decent living energy requirements. The chosen thresholds are in line with existing literature (Millward-Hopkins et al. 2020; Kikstra et al., 2021; Millward-Hopkins, 2022; Rao & Min, 2018a; Velez-Henao & Pauliuk, 2023, Kikstra et al. 2025, [Streeck et al. 2025](#), [Velez-Henao et al. 2025](#)). For a longer justification, see for instance Millward-Hopkins et al. (2020) and Kikstra et al. (2021).

Table 1: Activity levels used for Decent Living Standards analysis

Dimension	Activity
Nutrition	Country-specific minimum daily energy requirement (1653-2066 kcal/cap/day)
Cooking	1/hh
Cold storage	1/hh
Housing	11.2 m ² /cap residential floorspace based on global median household size (3.6 pers/hh)
Thermal comfort	Heating: up to 20°C Cooling: down to 26°C
Water	65 l/cap/day
Water heating	30 l/cap/day
Sanitation	Provided to all
Clothing	Clothing [kg/yr]: Global South: 1.3, Global North: 2.4 Footwear [kg/yr]: Global: 0.9
Health	\$1024/cap/yr
Education	Primary: \$1400/student/yr Lower secondary: \$2843/student/yr
Phone	1/hh
Bigger screen	1/hh
Mobility	Country-specific thresholds following a lived-density-based formula from Millward-Hopkins et al. (2020): 3548 – 15000 km/cap/yr
Roads	1.5 km paved road/km ² arable land

3. Quantification of just corridors

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Planning a sustainable, more efficient system can reduce energy needs for DLS. Importantly, not all activities in countries are used to satisfy basic needs, with significant energy use related to energy excess or luxury consumption. This means that both the purpose of energy use, and importantly the inequality (Oswald et al., 2020) within countries need to be studied to understand paths towards a just future with DLS for all, separating human needs, prosperity, and excessive use of resources (Pauliuk, 2024). Current regional (Jaccard et al., 2021; Kikstra et al., 2024; Millward-Hopkins & Johnson, 2023) and global (Millward-Hopkins, 2022; Millward-Hopkins & Oswald, 2023; Schlesier et al., 2024) analyses provide limited tools to model the energy availability for achieving DLS lacking either dynamics (changes in the energy system and emissions) or spatial and sectoral detail.

IAMs have been used to help understand multidimensional future socioeconomic scenarios with climate and environmental information for decades. Several studies have investigated the simultaneous achievement of multiple dimensions of the UN SDGs (McCollum et al., 2018; Soergel, Kriegler, Bodirsky, et al., 2021; Soergel, Kriegler, Weindl, et al., 2021; Van Vuuren et al., 2015). However, the representations of SDGs in existing literature are not complete (Orbons et al., 2024; van Soest et al., 2019), and models especially struggle to capture the challenges faced by the poor and vulnerable, since social heterogeneity within model regions is lacking (Rao et al., 2017). Even while many energy access studies exist (Pachauri et al., 2013; Poblete-Cazenave et al., 2021), when studies with IAMs do investigate within-country distributions explicitly (Emmerling et al., 2024; Soergel, Kriegler, Bodirsky, et al., 2021), representation of inequalities beyond monetary indicators is often missing.

No tool exists that links multiple sectors of IAMs to energy needs for DLS on a global scale. The Decent living standards and the Environment in Scenarios considering Inequality and Resource Efficiency (DESIRE) model fills this gap by introducing a framework that bridges the bottom-up literature on the energy needs for DLS with more aggregate IAMs. While there is no fundamental reason that prevents the endogenous modelling of DLS achievement in IAMs, its implementation is complex and would need to overcome many data limitations. This work aims to enable a more consistent treatment and assessment of inequality-growth-efficiency interactions (Figure 1), in relation to energy needs. Comprehensive tools for assessing such interactions across multiple sectors in climate mitigation pathways are currently lacking. The purpose here is to assess whether these scenarios can feasibly support DLS for all from an energy perspective, offering insights on the energy requirements of decent living to guide and inform climate mitigation strategies that also support important developmental needs.

Some use more energy than others: within-country distributions

Three levers for closing decent living gaps

Figure 1: A visual representation of inequality-growth-efficiency interactions distributed within a population with energy needs. The DESIRE model should track changes in energy availability for end-use services (i.e. growing the pie, shifting the distribution), reducing inequality (i.e. compressing the distribution of consumption), and improving service provisioning efficiency (i.e. lowering the minimum energy requirement for providing decent living standards).

With these concepts in mind, we define a few related terms (Figure 2), following Kikstra et al. (2025): *Energy needs*: the minimum energy requirements for meeting DLS, also known as the Decent Living Energy (DLE) threshold. *Deprivation headcount*: the estimated population consuming less energy than the minimum energy per capita required to provide DLS. *Energy needs gap* (also known as *DLE gap*): the amount of additional energy necessary to lift all those below the minimum up to the DLE threshold (DLET). *Energy headroom*: the energy left after subtracting the DLET from the total energy use. Total energy use can be split between *Energy provided for DLS* and *Energy beyond DLS*.

Terminology for Decent Living Energy concepts

Deprivation headcount
(population below DLE threshold)

Energy needs gap (=DLE gap)
(sum of all additional energy required to lift the full population to at least the DLE threshold)

Figure 2: A visual illustration of various concepts for decent living gaps and their related energy requirements.

3.1 Modelling minimum needs using the DESIRE model

The DESIRE model permits a consistent and dynamic interpretation of energy inequalities of IAM pathways, thus supporting the creation and evaluation of energy and emission scenarios. DESIRE is primarily targeted at linking with global IAMs, and its key inputs are tabular time series data. It is designed to supplement models with structural change in energy systems, to add the otherwise missing endogenous representations of within-country energy inequality or energy requirements for DLS. This dynamic framework (for a flowchart, see Figure 3) quantifies future changes in country-level final energy consumption, within-country inequality, and service provisioning efficiency, for energy consumption and energy needs to meet DLS related to three sectors; 'Residential and Commercial', 'Industry' (including feedstocks, agriculture, and fishing), and 'Transportation' (including bunker fuels, excluding pipelines). The aggregation of DLS constituents to these three sectors should be seen as a data limitation and is not an indication that the constituents of DLS within these sectors are substitutable. While in this version, the DLS constituents and their thresholds do not change over time, what is changing is *how* they are provided in the IAM pathways, and thus also the amount of (final) energy required to support DLS is changing. For instance, for transport, the modal share changes over time, and the efficiency of cars changes as electric vehicles become more common. For buildings, heat pumps are introduced and building standards change. DESIREv1.0.0 covers over 97% of the global population. An extended model description, including the calculation of model output, is available in Kikstra et al. 2025).

Figure 3: Flow chart design of the DESIRE model as represented in Kikstra et al. (2025), including other sources of data input, where the 'decent living standards and resource needs' module builds on Kikstra et al (2021).

3.2 Current energy needs at the national level

We build on the service-driven energy accounting model in Kikstra et al. (2021) to calculate the direct (operational) and indirect (construction) energy use required for delivering each aspect of DLS presented in Table 1. These energy services are mapped onto the more aggregate 3-way territorial *Residential and Commercial, Transportation, Industry* sectors available in IAMs.

Current energy requirements vary between countries (Figure 4; Kikstra et al., 2021; Millward-Hopkins et al., 2020; Rao, Min, et al., 2019). Taking the 5–95th percentile across countries, we find 4-11 GJ for the residential and commercial sector, 7-22 for transportation, 2-7 for industry, and a total of 13-40 GJ/cap/yr. National circumstances lead to a considerable variation in energy needs based on for instance the climate and current provisioning systems, with modal shares of passenger transportation being the biggest single factor in explaining differences between countries (Kikstra et al., 2021).

Global average per capita DLETs are estimated at 6.4 GJ for the residential and commercial sector, 3.4 for the industry, and 10.7 for transportation, with a total of 20.5 GJ/cap/yr.

One important note to keep in mind is that the DLET above includes operational energy and construction energy for replacing the infrastructure (depending on the assumed lifetime of different products). It does not include new construction, which depend on the speed of building new infrastructures. This means that this DLET is a

lower bound, and that during the construction period especially higher industrial energy thresholds may be required (see Section 4).

Figure 4: DLE threshold energy requirements per capita, mapped onto three sectors, based on current technologies, as a global average (top) and for three representative countries (bottom)

4. Current energy needs gaps

We combine our energy needs data with data on annual energy use per country to calculate how large the energy needs gap is in each country, for each sector, following the methodology described in Kikstra et al. (2025). Energy use by region and sector is modelled using the MESSAGEix-GLOBIOM integrated assessment model (Krey et al., 2020) and downscaled using the DSCALE model (Sferra et al., 2025).

Africa and Southern Asia account for the majority of the current global energy deprivation, as illustrated in Figure 5. The figure highlights the regional breakdown of energy shortfalls across key sectors, showing that in both Africa and Southern Asia, the most significant energy gap is found in the transportation sector. This sector has the highest energy intensity, meaning it requires a large amount of energy relative to its output, and it also displays the largest rates of deprivation—suggesting a severe lack of access to adequate fuel and infrastructure for mobility.

In Southern Asia, the figure shows that the industrial energy gap is comparatively small. This reflects the region's ongoing industrialisation, which has led to growing manufacturing capacity and relatively better energy provision for factories and production facilities. However, this progress is uneven: the region continues to face significant shortages in the residential and commercial sectors, where access to residential and commercial energy remains limited.

Africa stands out in Figure 5 as having the largest per-capita energy gaps among all regions. The data underscore how widespread and deep this deprivation is—Africa's energy shortfall amounts to more than half of its current total energy consumption. This means that to meet basic development needs, the continent would need to more than double its energy supply.

Figure 5: Energy needs and gaps per capita across world regions, aggregated from 172 countries. The filled part of the bars indicates the part of the energy need already fulfilled in 2025, while the white part indicates the energy needs gap.

5. Emissions in providing energy for Decent Living Standards

The emissions for achieving DLS for all depend strongly on the energy system of the country and its future climate policies. The global average CO₂ emissions for DLS based on the global energy system in 2020 is about 2 tCO₂ per capita per year. The 5–95th percentile across countries ranges from close to zero (due to low-carbon energy systems) to around 4 tCO₂ per capita.

Relatively low emissions implied in DLS provisioning are found in Sub-Saharan Africa and South Asia (Figure 6). These are regions with medium-low energy requirements such as Southern Asia, for instance due to lower heating needs and high public transport shares of transportation. Some countries, including Ethiopia, Singapore, Bhutan, and Iceland, have currently low emissions in the energy system, for instance due to a very high bioenergy use or high shares of hydropower or geothermal. In contrast, North America currently has very high emissions for DLS for all due to very high energy requirements (especially for transportation) and a fossil-fuel dominated energy system.

Figure 6: Current energy and emissions per capita for DLS.

To meet climate targets, emissions need to be reduced. Considering that the remaining carbon budget is vanishingly small at only 130 GtCO₂ from the beginning of 2025 (Forster et al., 2025), overshooting the 1.5 °C target seems unavoidable. While the remaining carbon budget may thus be of little guidance, pathways towards pursuing 1.5 °C or staying well-below 2 °C can still be pursued (Rogelj & Rajamani, 2025), limiting overshoot, tipping risks, and climate impacts (Schleussner et al., 2024).

To illustrate, we look at a set of pathways with limited overshoot to provide guidance on staying within a just corridor. We choose the scenarios analysed in the Mitigation report of the Sixth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (Byers et al., 2022; IPCC, 2022), specifically those in the C1 ("limit warming to 1.5°C (>50%) with no or limited overshoot") and C3 ("limit warming to 2°C (>67%)") climate categories.

We then show how a new, standard, MESSAGEix-GLOBIOM scenario compares to this range, for both energy use and fossil CO₂ emissions. First, we recognise that it might make intuitive sense to also think about a safe boundaries defined in terms of energy per capita consumption because we quantified the floor in terms of energy consumption. Energy use is one of the drivers of emissions. Emissions are connected to climate change, which is widely recognised as one of the planetary boundaries (Rockström et al., 2009).

However, the connection between energy and emissions is not constant. While we select scenarios with strong mitigation policies, which reduce emissions (Figure 7) and stabilise global temperatures, energy use per capita (Figure 8) does not necessarily decline.

The MESSAGEix-GLOBIOM scenario that we use in this report is mostly in line with the IPCC C3 category, with a carbon budget of around 520 GtCO₂ between 2025 and 2100.

Figure 7: Fossil CO₂ emissions (“Emissions|CO₂|Energy and Industrial Processes”) in scenarios from the IPCC AR6 Scenario Database and the MESSAGE Reference mitigation scenario.

Figure 8: Final energy use ("Final Energy") in scenarios from the IPCC AR6 Scenario Database and the MESSAGE Reference mitigation scenario. In the AR6 Scenario Databases, these variables are not harmonized and therefore there is significant variation in the starting point.

6. Incorporation of DLS into MESSAGEix

Disclaimer

Part of this text is adapted from the publications:

- Kikstra, Jarmo S., et al. (2025). "Closing decent living gaps in energy and emissions scenarios: introducing DESIRE". *Environmental Research Letters* 20, 054038.
- IIASA. "JustMIP Protocol: Advancing Climate Justice Considerations in IAM Scenarios." Zenodo (2025). DOI [10.5281/zenodo.15647134](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15647134)

Introduction of scenarios

Past studies have shown that ensuring universal access to key energy services may lead to increased energy demand and associated emissions, depending on the climate policy and how equally resources are distributed (Huo et al., 2023; Kikstra et al., 2021, 2025; McElroy & O'Neill, 2025; Millward-Hopkins & Oswald, 2023; Rammelt et al., 2023; Schlesier et al., 2024). Here, we explore two scenario variants (Figure 9) that both achieve the same climate target, but we have a “**Reference**” mitigation scenario that follows the SSP2 storyline while a “**Minimum Needs**” (MN) variant, assumes additional energy and service provision sufficient to ensure that all individuals currently below the DLS are brought up to minimum energy thresholds. The reference mitigation scenario stays within a carbon budget of 800 GtCO₂. The closing of gaps starts after 2025, and is fulfilled in 2040 in this scenario.

We set 2040 as the year of DLS achievement, giving an ambitious 15 years for the provisioning of infrastructure, which is equally long as was given between the publication and target of the Millennium Development Goals, as well as the SDGs. In our modelling, the rate of closing decent living gaps will be kept constant, starting the buildout of new DLS-provisioning infrastructure directly after 2025, until 2040. Roughly speaking, this is expected to result in a (near) linear increase of additional energy demand in transport and buildings, starting from 0 in 2025 until the full DLE difference (=energy needs gap) in 2040. Until (& including) 2040, this includes energy for constructing commensurate new infrastructure to support expanding DLS access. After 2040, full DLS infrastructure is already there, and the remaining additional energy is based only on “contemporary energy” gaps in the underlying reference scenario (i.e., operational energy and energy for replacing infrastructure). This also means that immediately post-2040, a drop in (industry) energy demand can be observed in regions that require significant new infrastructure.

In this implementation, the energy quantification for closing decent living gaps is taken as the ‘modeling entry-point’. As IAMs are used to quantify scenarios that are internally consistent, it is important that the model implementation subsequently takes care of system knock-on effects such as changes in the economy, energy efficiency, land-use, water demand, etc. This approach - using IAMs - is a complementary approach to calculating multiple resource requirements using life-cycle analysis with regional, product-level information (e.g. Velez-Henao et al. 2025 for water, land, energy, and GHGs), with the advantage in IAMs being the consistent projection of changes in the future, such as the analysis of climate mitigation.

Figure 9: Scenarios variants of alternative living standard achievements (visualised), with Reference scenarios on the left, and the MN variants on the right.

These scenarios do not a-priori assume or prescribe specific policy instruments to achieve the proposed final energy reductions of the wealthy but explore a quantitative range consistent with different aggregate mean living standards. As in previous studies (Millward-Hopkins & Oswald, 2021, 2023), the goal is to explore the implications of such final energy demand increases and reductions for climate targets—and, in our setup, for transformations in the energy system as well, in line with explicitly assumed climate mitigation policies.

To systematically examine the implications of meeting minimum needs - defined as achieving DLS for all - for meeting climate mitigation targets, we run these two scenario variants with the same 800 GtCO₂ carbon budget. From this, we learn different regional efforts with and without minimum needs achievement.

Calculation of energy demand adjustments as multiplication factors

We downscale the final energy in the Reference scenario to get country-level energy demand per capita by sector, (b) run DESIRE to get the energy needs gap for this scenario (s), for each region (r), variable (v), and point in time (t). Next, we remove non-clean residential and part of commercial energy to obtain clean energy use per capita (x) that is aligned with DLS provisioning.

The energy needs gap ENG is calculated following the methods of Kikstra et al. (2025). It is the sum of the energy gap of each person consuming less energy than a (sectoral)

DLET. We obtain this by integrating from 0 to the DLET along the energy consumption distribution function $p(x)$ where x is (clean) energy use per capita:

$$ENG = \int_0^{DLET} (DLET - x) p(x) dx$$

Energy Gini coefficients are estimated following Kikstra et al. (2025) too, with changes in the SSP2 scenario driven by changes in income inequality following (Rao, Sauer, et al., 2019). Energy consumption distributions are based on existing data (Oswald et al., 2020). The energy use distribution is assumed to be lognormal, capturing a long tail on the higher end of the distribution. For energy consumption – as opposed to income or wealth – this distributional form can be seen as a pragmatic and parsimonious option which works relatively well (for a detailed discussion, see supplementary Section 2.2 of Kikstra et al. 2025).

The lognormal distribution ($Lognormal(\mu, \sigma^2)$) is defined by the mean energy consumption per capita and the projected energy consumption Gini, following:

$$\mu = \ln(\text{EnergyPerCapita}) - \frac{\sigma^2}{2} \text{ where } \sigma = \sqrt{2} \cdot \text{invcdf}(\text{normal}(), (\text{EnergyGiniCoefficient} + 1)/2)$$

We do the calculations on the final energy level. The reason for this is the combination of data availability and ability to reflect structural changes (in service provisioning efficiency). While the calculations of the ENG are done on the level of final energy, they are meant to proxy the relative increase of services necessary to lift people up to DLS. In increasing energy use in the scenarios using these multiplication factors, modelling teams should ensure that the additional energy demand is fulfilled with clean energy, avoiding the use of traditional biomass (which comes with negative health impacts through air pollution).

The building of new infrastructure (e.g., housing or roads) to support development is considered, too. This is based on the gap in provisioning observed in 2025, but we avoid double-counting of new DLS-supporting infrastructure that is already integrated in the MESSAGE Reference scenario (as indicated by the closing of the energy needs gap and the reduction of the deprivation headcount).

Subsequently, we translate these final energy calculations to useful energy following MESSAGE-specific factors over time. We adjust GDP up accordingly, using a constant energy-to-GDP elasticity. Then, we recalibrate MESSAGE-MACRO to the newly obtained (useful) energy demand and GDP time series, and calculate the new MN scenario.

An overview is presented in Figure 10.

The Creation of a Minimum Needs Scenario

Figure 10: Generalized methods of this exercise, where the Reference scenario is the “1000f, 900f, ...”, MESSAGEix-GLOBIOM is “MESSAGE”, and MN is the “w/o RD” option, respectively.

7. Initial results

First, we look at how the MESSAGE model projections affect energy and emissions implied in DLS provisioning.

Climate policies (lower fossil emissions) and service provisioning efficiency improvements (lower energy requirements for the same set of energy services) lead to strong declines in the fossil emissions implied in DLS provisioning for all regions, by 2050 (Figure 11).

This is in line with expectations from recent literature (Kikstra et al., 2025) and illustrates the possibility to create societies that provide minimum needs without leading to additional global emissions. While the type of climate policies and service provisioning efficiency improvements, and their representations in different models indeed changes, the results presented here are in line with the findings for the REMIND-MAgPIE and IMAGE models (Kikstra et al., 2025). There is thus broad agreement that minimum energy requirements can be reduced, and emissions implied in DLS provisioning can go to net-zero.

Globally, in the Reference scenario, average minimum energy requirements drop from 20.5 GJ/cap/yr in 2025 to 14.4 GJ/cap/yr in 2050.

2050 energy and emissions per capita for DLS

With change since 2025

Figure 11: 2050 energy and emissions per capita for DLS compared to 2025 values in the MESSAGE Reference mitigation scenario.

Second, we look at the size of the energy needs gaps that are filled in the MN scenario.

While the global decent living energy gap declines from 45 to 28 EJ/yr, global energy use still falls short of providing DLS for all, especially in Africa and South Asia, with transportation being the most energy-deprived sector.

We find relatively modest energy increases in the buildings sector and industry for all regions except Africa, while transportation energy gaps are large (Figure 12). The increase from building new infrastructure until 2040 is generally modest compared to the increase in other energy consumption, but it is clear that especially sub-Saharan Africa requires large amounts of new infrastructure.

Achieving DLS for all by 2040, like in the MN scenario, increases global energy demand modestly (4% in 2030, 9% in 2040, 5% in 2050), but significantly increases in

Sub-Saharan Africa (35% in 2030, 68% in 2040, 31% in 2050), the region with the highest DLS deprivation.

Figure 12: Required energy increase to meet DLS for all in 2040 and afterwards, expressed in percentage increase (of useful energy) relative to the Reference mitigation scenario.

Finally, we show how regional emissions and energy systems differ between the Reference and MN scenarios, which both have the same carbon budget until 2100.

In Global South regions, we find somewhat higher emissions during the development phase (Figure 13) when energy needs gaps are closed. In Africa, this effect dominates the long-term effect of climate policy until 2050, while in Southern Asia the climate policy starts dominating emissions trends around 2040 and after. Other regions compensate for these increased emissions, sometimes with earlier emissions reductions, and sometimes with more carbon removal in the second half of the century.

Figure 13: CO₂ emissions for the MN and Reference scenarios for two of the Global South regions with the largest energy gaps in the Reference scenario, and North America and Europe as examples of Global North regions.

In Global South regions we see a virtually unchanged coal phase-out, indicating that, under the assumption of cost-effective climate policy, it is not necessary to delay coal phase-out to meet energy demand for DLS (Figure 14). This indicates that renewables can cover part of the increase in electricity demand (Figure 15). Oil does see an increase (Figure 14), driven by the strong increase in energy demand for transportation (Figure 12), with not all regions being able to provide fully electrified transport early. The direction of change for natural gas consumption depends on the region.

Figure 14: Primary energy futures for the MN and Reference scenarios for three Global South regions with large populations, and North America as an example of a Global North region.

Figure 15: Electricity and solar and wind energy futures for the MN and Reference scenarios for three Global South regions with large populations, and Europe and North America as examples of Global North regions.

In all regions, we see some increase in energy use until mid-century (Figure 16), with by far the largest per-capita increase seen in Africa, which also requires large energy footprints during the DLS provisioning rollout. However, even while the increase is large, it should be noted that even by 2050, when everyone is modelled to have DLS or higher, there is a large variety of energy use per capita between regions (Figure 16). In other words, DLS can be met at low levels of average final energy per capita, with very low levels of within-region inequality, and thus very small portions of the population that are high energy consumers. Declines in final energy use per capita in Europe and North America are mostly due to energy efficiency improvements.

Despite the Minimum Needs related increase relative to the Reference scenarios, also in the MN scenario global final energy use is only <3% higher in 2050 than in 2025.

Figure 16: Energy use futures for the MN and Reference scenarios for three Global South regions with large populations, and Europe and North America as examples of Global North regions.

8. Discussion and conclusion

Our analysis reveals insights about the trajectory and implications of achieving DLS in a climate-constrained world.

Achieving DLS under the Minimum Needs (MN) pathway causes only a modest increase in energy consumption: 4% in 2030, 9% in 2040, 5% in 2050. However, in regions like Sub-Saharan Africa, the rise is substantial (+35% in 2030, peaking at +68% in 2040), not only requiring a large increase in energy consumption for transportation and household energy use, but also energy for building out new infrastructure. Globally, by 2050, final energy in the MN scenario is less than 3% higher than in 2025.

Although there is more energy activity in Africa and slight adjustments elsewhere, the overall transition pathway holds steady. Importantly, timelines for coal phase-out are

not delayed in developing regions under the MN scenario, indicating that rising electricity needs can be met without reverting to fossil fuel lock-in.

Emissions trajectories remain within the same carbon budget through a combination of clean-energy deployment and accelerated decarbonization elsewhere. This reaffirms that provisioning decent living can be made compatible with stringent climate goals, especially when equity is embedded in policy design.

Our theoretical pathways suggest that low average final energy per capita can suffice for universal DLS – but only under conditions of extremely low inequality. This emphasizes that per-capita energy targets alone are insufficient; distribution matters. Narrow energy disparities facilitate decent living without forcing high average energy use.

In sum, while the route to sustainability under the MN scenario involves big shifts in sub-Saharan Africa, we only observe relatively moderate shifts for most regions. This suggests that providing DLS for all does not require rewriting the global energy transition blueprint.

We model energy-system transitions without delving into the economics and feasibility of infrastructure build-outs and strong within-region inequality reductions. Regions with high upfront capital needs (e.g., electrified transport, building or retrofitting durable housing) can face difficulties in mobilising enough investment and may require global support. The modest energy and emissions implications may therefore underestimate broader barriers in a real-world rollout. Similarly, socioeconomic and geographic heterogeneity, including cultural preferences and infrastructural locking may affect the real-life feasibility of meeting DLS at the relatively low energy footprints that we simulate.

Lastly, ensuring DLS comes with resource implications beyond energy. While our IAM takes care of this in an aggregate manner, we have explicitly analysing additional resource requirements is beyond the scope of this report. For instance, material use (construction materials, appliances, vehicles), land-use (roads, buildings, agriculture), and water consumption are likely to intensify with a DLS rollout, and would bring additional nuance to the picture painted in this report. Our framework could be expanded to include such elements in future work (e.g. Streeck et al. 2025, Velez-Henao et al. 2025).

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